

Trends in the trace level determination of amino acids using selective fluorescent probes : A critical survey

Mili Dutta^{a*} and Debasis Das^{b*}

^aBurdwan Harisava Hindu Girl's High School (Morning), Burdwan, West Bengal, India

^bDepartment of Chemistry, The University of Burdwan, Burdwan-713 104, West Bengal, India

E-mail : ddas100in@yahoo.com Fax : 91-342-2530452

Manuscript received online 27 February 2012, revised 01 April 2012, accepted 16 April 2012

Abstract : Trace level determination of amino acids is an important and highly relevant area of biochemistry and molecular biology. Herein, we have illustrated different fluorescent probes that have been developed so far for trace level determination of different amino acids. The fluorescence method is highly sensitive, selective, rapid, user friendly and non-destructive. Definitely it is a greener and superior technique compared to other analytical methods. A critical survey of the fluorescent sensors of each type of amino acids, viz. acidic, basic and neutral has been made. A separate section discusses about the sensors which can detect multiple amino acids simultaneously. Novelty and demerits of the methods have been described briefly. Finally, a future prospect in this field has been sketched.

Keywords : Fluorescent probes, amino acids, trace level determination, analytical figures of merit, cell imaging, biological samples.

Introduction

Amino acids, the building blocks of proteins, are the indispensable units of our body. The stunning diversity of the thousands of proteins found in nature arises from the intrinsic properties of only twenty naturally occurring amino acids. Out of them only nine amino acids are essential for humans (Fig. 1).

Amino acids have certain typical properties, i.e. polymerization, chirality, novel acid-base properties and varied structural and chemical functionalities in the side chains. Except glycine, all other amino acids isolated from proteins have four different groups attached to the alpha-carbon, giving rise to its chirality.

A wide array of methods has been used for the detection and quantification of amino acids which include spectroscopic methods (UV-Vis, NMR and FTIR), chromatographic techniques like HPLC, capillary electrophoresis and circular dichroism methods. However use of fluorescence sensors for the determination of amino acids has been of particular interest due to their selectivity, robustness, sensitivity, least interference and non-destructive methodology.

Fluorescent chemosensors are gaining importance in the fields of environmental monitoring, food processing, biomedical technology, and clinical analysis. They are being widely applied in chemical sensing and bio-sensing^{1,2}.

The volume of work in this field has been growing significantly during the last few years as it appears from the literature survey (Fig. 2).

The sources of all the information are online literature search engines like Scopus and Chemistry Citation Index. An exhaustive survey of all the leading high impact journals including American Chemical Society, Royal Society of Chemistry, Wiley, Springer, Elsevier, Taylor & Francis and many more has also been carried out. We have been careful that no relevant work is left out of study.

A fluorescent chemosensor (host) recognizes a guest analyte by changing its fluorescence signal, due to the perturbation processes like photoinduced electron or energy transfer (PET), formation or disappearance of excimers or exciplexes³⁻⁵. The extent of host-guest interaction is measured as a change in fluorescence intensity,

Fig. 1. Structures of essential amino acids.

intensity decay lifetime or a shift in emission wavelength. Among the different mechanisms of fluorescence signal transduction, PET and intermolecular charge transfer (ICT) are the most common.

Fig. 2. Relative number of works (%) on the determination of amino acids using fluorescent probes (from ~2000-2011, December).

During the molecular design of a chemosensor, the specific recognition of a molecule followed by the trans-

duction of the recognition event into a detectable signal is important⁶. The receptor may be considered to be the central processing unit (CPU) of a chemosensor. For chiral molecules, the specific receptor should be covalently linked to an optical signaling unit (fluorophore)^{7,8}.

For a PET chemosensor, a fluorophore is usually connected via a spacer to a receptor containing a relatively high energy non-bonding electron pair which can transfer the electron pair to the excited fluorophore resulting in quenching of fluorescence. Binding of the electron pair to the analyte enhances its redox potential to inhibit the PET process resulting in appearance of fluorescence. However, fluorescent sensors that work through ratiometric mechanism⁹ can inherently avoid the effect of surrounding environments like temperature, polarity of media and probe concentration, as the ratios of the two emission intensities (at one wavelength, intensity increases while in the other it decreases) are measured as a function of externally added analyte concentration. ICT mechanism has been widely used in the design of ratiometric fluores-

cent sensors. Whenever a fluorophore without a spacer is directly connected to a receptor (usually an amino group) to form a π -electron conjugation system with electron rich/electron poor terminals, ICT from the electron donor to receptor would be enhanced upon excitation by light.

Electron donor-acceptor interactions play a fundamental role in these processes. Binding with the guest induces a change in the output signal (fluorescence) as shown in Fig. 3. Also, it should be noted that on the basis of good binding selectivity, the fluorescence signal should avoid environmental interferences (signal selectivity), such as photo-bleaching, sensor molecule concentration, and stability under illumination.

interference from other amino acids is a still a challenging task.

In this review, a detailed investigation on the use of various fluorescence probes for trace level determination of acidic, basic and neutral amino acids has been made. In fact, literature survey reveals that compared to the large number of fluoro-receptors for cations and anions, the development of artificial receptors for amino acids is rather low and still a challenging theme due to their strong hydrophilic character.

We have systematically discussed the developments of the fluorescent probes for the determination of trace level amino acids in the order : acidic amino acids, basic

Fig. 3. Donor-acceptor interaction induced fluorescent properties.

Chirality is another typical phenomenon of amino acids, hence the design of enantioselective fluorescent sensors for amino acids is particularly important. By introducing chirality into the binding site, the resulting fluorescent chemosensor can carry out the enantioselective recognition of chiral molecules. Just like other chiral molecules, the chemical properties and biological activity of amino acids are dependent on their stereochemistry; each enantiomer may have different pharmacological properties in terms of activity, potency, toxicity, transport mechanism and metabolic route.

Recently, many efforts involve the covalent linking of an optical signaling unit (a chromophore or a fluorophore) to a specific receptor for the anion or chiral molecules¹⁰⁻¹³. Fluorescence techniques have often been used to study the interaction between enantiomers and receptors because of their sensitivity, selectivity, and versatility¹⁴. Selective detection of a specific amino acid without in-

terference from other amino acids, neutral amino acids and finally the sensors which can simultaneously determine more than one amino acid. Fig. 4 shows the molecular structures of various amino acid selective fluorescent probes. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first of its kind and we believe that this article will be very helpful to the researchers working or interested in the field of trace level detection and estimation of amino acids in biological samples. We also feel that use of fluorescent probes for trace level determination of amino acids has the potentiality to be marked as a green method compared to other existing methods like HPLC and its allied techniques.

Fluorescent probes selective for acidic amino acids

Aspartic and glutamic acid :

Aspartate and glutamate are major excitatory amino acids (EAAs) that activate N-methyl-d-aspartate (NMDA) receptors in the mammalian central nervous system (CNS), and have been found to play an important role in learn-

A1 [25]

A2 [26]

A3 [27]

A4 [28]

A5 [29]

(a)

(b)

(c)

L1 [32]

Fig. 4 (Contd.)

Ag Cluster
C3 [43]

Fig. 4 (Contd.)

Fig. 4 (Contd.)

Fig. 4. Molecular structures of the amino acid selective fluorescent probes.

ing, memory, movement disorders, drug addiction as well as many other normal or abnormal physiological processes and behaviors. A disturbance in the relative balance of aspartic acid (Asp) and glutamic acid (Glu) may cause several neurological or psychiatric disorders¹⁵⁻¹⁸. Massive efflux of Asp and Glu has been observed in different neuro-pathological models of brain injury^{19,20} which caused an uncontrolled excitotoxic stimulation of postsyn-

aptic (mainly NMDA) receptors, membrane depolarization and energy depletion resulting in neuronal cell death²¹. Pathological release of Asp and Glu into the extracellular fluid has been found to cause the deterioration of retinal ganglion cells after traumatic or ischemic damage to the CNS, leading to glaucoma²²⁻²⁴.

Liu *et al.* synthesized a fluorescent dicarboxylate receptor (A1) developed from cholic acid which had great

Table 1. Characteristics of aspartic and glutamic acid sensitive fluorescent sensors

Sensor	Type	Medium	LOD	Binding constant (M^{-1})	Ref.
A1	Turn off	Methanol/water	-	$(5.57 \pm 0.88) \times 10^6$	25
A2	Turn on	Aqueous	$3.2 \times 10^{-8} M$ for Asp and $5.7 \times 10^{-8} M$ for Glu	-	26
A3	Turn on	DMSO	-	34.3 ± 5.0 (N-Ac-L-Glu) 26.9 ± 3.7 (N-Ac-D-Glu)	27
A4	Turn off	DMSO	-	(S,S) = 959.6 ± 75.7 (L-aspartate) (S,S) = 148.2 ± 12.7 (D-aspartate) (R,R) = 126.8 ± 16.6 (L-aspartate) (R,R) = 854.3 ± 50.7 (D-aspartate)	28
A5	Turn on	Aqueous	-	4357.8 (Asp) 8333.3 (Glu)	29

Table 2. Characteristics of lysine sensitive fluorescent sensors

Sensor	Type	Medium	LOD	Binding constant/log K/K_d	Ref.
L1	Turn on	CH ₃ OH	-	log $K = 2.25$ (a) log $K = 2.16$ (b) log $K = 4.7$ (c)	32
L2	Turn on	CH ₃ CN-HEPES buffer		K_d (L2-lysine) = 2.78×10^{-3}	33
L3	Turn on	CH ₃ OH			34

Table 3. Characteristics of histidine sensitive fluorescent sensors

Sensor	Type	Medium	LOD	Binding constant (M^{-1})	Ref.
H1	Turn on	CH ₂ Cl ₂	$2 \times 10^{-3} M$	$K = 1.5 \times 10^4$	35
H2	Turn on	HEPES buffer		$K = 1.0 \times 10^{7.2}$	36

Table 4. Characteristics of cysteine sensitive fluorescent sensors

Sensor	Type	Medium	LOD	Binding constant	Ref.
C1	Turn on	Water/ethanol 3 : 2			41
C2	Turn on	Aqueous	$25 \times 10^{-9} M$	-	42
C3 (Ag cluster)	Turn off	Aqueous	$2 \times 10^{-8} M$	-	43
C4	Turn on and Turn off	Aqueous ethanol	-	-	44

Table 5. Characteristics of glycine sensitive fluorescent sensors

Sensor	Type	Medium	LOD	Binding constant (M^{-1})	Ref.
G1	Turn on	Benzene in 2% dimethoxyethylene	-	-	45
G2	Turn on	DMSO	-	$2.96 \pm 0.16 \times 10^4$ (L) $5.26 \pm 0.25 \times 10^3$ (D)	46

affinity for glutamate, specially towards L-glutamate and its *N*-protected derivatives than their simple dicarboxylate in methanol/water system²⁵.

A composite of a water soluble fluorescent polythiophene derivative (A2) and gold nanoparticles have been

developed as an efficient turn on fluorescence detector for Asp and Glu²⁶. The “superquenching” property of the gold nanoparticles has been applied to polythiophene derivatives for detecting Asp and Glu in pure water. An increase in fluorescence intensity occurred on addition of

Table 6. Characteristics of alanine/phenylalanine sensitive fluorescent sensors

Sensor	Type	Medium	LOD	Binding constant (M^{-1})	Ref.
A1 1	Turn off	Chloroform		(2.30 ± 0.19) $\times 10^4$ (L-alanine) (for a) (1.32 ± 0.14) $\times 10^4$ (L-Ph-alanine) (for a) (1.01 ± 0.13) $\times 10^3$ (D-Ph-alanine) (for a) (1.08 ± 0.14) $\times 10^3$ (L-alanine) (for b) (1.94 ± 0.15) $\times 10^3$ (L-Ph-alanine) (for b) (0.73 ± 0.06) $\times 10^3$ (D-Ph-alanine) (for b)	48
A1 2	Turn off	DMSO		53.56 \pm 2.91 (D-N-Boc-Ala) 28.79 \pm 2.97 (L-N-Boc-Phe) 32.24 \pm 1.70 (D-N-Boc-Phe)	49
A1 3	Turn off	Chloroform		a : (3.90 ± 0.12) $\times 10^4$ (S-alanine) a : (5.43 ± 0.03) $\times 10^3$ (R-alanine) a : (3.24 ± 0.04) $\times 10^4$ (S-Ph-alanine) a : (4.39 ± 0.12) $\times 10^3$ (R-Ph-alanine) b : (5.38 ± 0.10) $\times 10^3$ (S-alanine) b : (3.79 ± 0.21) $\times 10^4$ (R-alanine) b : (4.52 ± 0.12) $\times 10^3$ (S-Ph-alanine) b : (3.49 ± 0.07) $\times 10^4$ (R-Ph-alanine)	50
A1 4	Turn off	DMSO		(1.24 ± 0.10) $\times 10^4$ (D-Ph-alanine) (2.49 ± 0.23) $\times 10^3$ (L-Ph-alanine)	51
A1 5	Turn off	Acetonitrile		a : 1.18×10^4 (D- <i>t</i> -Boc-alanine) a : 2.16×10^3 (L- <i>t</i> -Boc-alanine) b : 2.30×10^3 (D- <i>t</i> -Boc-alanine) b : 2.39×10^3 (L- <i>t</i> -BOC-alanine)	52

Table 7. Characteristics of valine/proline sensitive fluorescent sensors

Sensor	Type	Medium	LOD	Binding constant	Ref.
PV 1	Turn off	Borate buffer (pH 7.0)	-	-	54, 55
PV 2	Turn on	Borate buffer (pH 7.3)	-	-	56
PV 3	Turn on	CH ₂ Cl ₂ /hexane (3 : 7), containing 1.2% THF	-	-	57

Table 8. Characteristics of tryptophan sensitive fluorescent sensors

Sensor	Type	Medium	LOD	Binding constant/log K	Ref.
Tryp 1	Turn off	Dioxane : water = 4 : 1 (v/v) at pH 7.0	-	log K = 4.28 ± 0.04	59
Tryp 2	FRET	Cacodylate buffer, pH = 7.0	-	$K_D = (7 \pm 5) \times 10^{-8} M$	60
Tryp 3	Turn on	DMSO		3157 M^{-1} (a); 2873 M^{-1} (b)	61

Asp and Glu to the polythiophene derivative and gold nanoparticles composite, that quantitatively reflected the amounts of Asp or Glu added. The composite was sensitive to environmental changes in pH.

Chiral recognition of amino acids is very important in various biochemical systems. Qing *et al.* have synthesized four linear thiourea anion receptors (A3) derived from amino acid, one of which showed good enantioselective response to the N-acetyl-glutamate²⁷. They have

also developed calix[4]arenes bearing dansyl fluorophore (A4) for the recognition of N-acetyl-glutamate²⁸. ¹H NMR experiments have revealed that hydrogen-bonding interaction between the host and guest was the main factor in the recognition process leading to a significant fluorescent enhancement. Recently our group has synthesized a weakly fluorescent cobalt(II) complex (A5) using 2-(2-pyridyl)-benzimidazole (PBI) as a chelating fluorescent ligand, which could efficiently determine trace levels of

Table 9. Characteristics of multi-amino acid sensitive fluorescent sensors

Sensor	Type	Medium	LOD	Binding constant	Ref.
MAA 1	Turn on	H ₂ O/MeOH (1/2, v/v)	-	-	62
MAA 2	Turn on	Acetonitrile	-	102 × 10 ⁷ M ⁻¹ (Glycine)	63
MAA 3	Turn on	THF-H ₂ O	0.2 ppm	-	64
MAA 4	Ratiometric	Dichloromethane	-	-	65
MAA 5	Turn on	Water	1.5-3 ppm	19400 ± 600	66
MAA 6	Turn off	DMSO	1.93 × 10 ⁻⁷ M for L-asparagine	log K ₂ = 3.91 ± 0.29 (Gabapentin) 2.90 ± 0.03 (Pregabalin) 4.01 ± 0.13 (Carnitine)	67
			3.09 × 10 ⁻⁶ M for GABA	3.33 ± 0.02 (Ceatine) 4.49 ± 0.02 (β-Alanine)	
			1.38 × 10 ⁻⁶ M for L-carnitine	log K ₂ = 3.01 ± 0.26 (Gabapentin) 3.06 ± 0.09 (Pregabalin) 3.80 ± 0.06 (Carniline) 3.93 ± 0.09 (β-Alanine)	
MAA 7	Turn on	Tris-buffer (pH 7-9.0)	-	-	68
MAA 8	Turn off	Borate buffer (0.1 M) at pH = 7	-	-	70
MAA 9	Turn on	HEPES buffer (pH=7.4)		3.98 × 10 ⁶ M ⁻¹ (Histidine)	71

Table 10. Use of metal complexes as amino acid selective fluorescent probe

Sensor	Metal-organic framework used	Amino acid detected	Ref.
A2	Polythiophene derivative-gold nanoparticles assembly	Aspartic and glutamic acid	26
A5	Bis-2-(2-pyridylbenzimidazole)Co ^{II} Cl ₂ complex	Aspartic and glutamic acid	29
H2	Fluorophore carboxylic acid bridged dinuclear Cu ^{II} complex of bis-(benzo-diethylenetriamine) derivative	Histidine	36
C3	Silver cluster	Cysteine	43
C4	<i>In situ</i> Fe ^{III} and Ag ^I complexes of C4	Cysteine	44
PV 1	Cu ^{II} complex of valine and proline	Valine and proline	54, 55
Tryp 1	Zn ^{II} complex of tripodal tetra-amino ligand bearing two anthracene unit	Tryptophan	59
MAA 3	Cu ^{II} complex of a conjugated polyfluorene derivative	Multiple α-amino acids	64
MAA 7	Cu ^{II} complex of quinacridone derivative	Multiple amino acids	68
MAA 9	Cu ^{II} complex of MAA 9	Histidine and cysteine	71

Asp and Glu in aqueous solution with minimum interference from rest of the naturally occurring amino acids²⁹.

As mentioned earlier, Asp and Glu levels play an extremely important role for different neurological disorders and based on this fact different novel neuro-pharmacological agents are being developed. Hence, more work on this area with applicability of the developed fluorescent probes over real samples would be of utmost use.

Fluorescent probes selective for basic amino acids

Lysine :

Lysine, another essential amino acid plays a significant role in Krebs's cycle and polyamine synthesis³⁰. Presence of high concentrations of this amino acid in the plasma and urine causes congenital metabolic disorders like cystinuria or hyperlysinemia³¹.

Luminescent crown ether amino acids (CEAA) (**L1**) have been synthesized by Mandl *et al.*³², which had affinity to ammonium ions and signaled the binding processes by an increase in fluorescent emission. A bis-ammonium guest, such as lysine methyl ester, was cooperatively bound with high affinity. Isomeric small peptides containing a lysine residue in different positions could be distinguished based on the differences in affinity of the bis-CEAA to bis-ammonium ions. The binding events of both crown ether groups were monitored independently by changes of their specific emission properties.

Zhou *et al.* have developed a pyrene based sensor³³ (**L2**) that has been employed as a suitable fluorescent sensor for lysine under neutral conditions, by fluorescence enhancement. The sensor detected lysine colorimetrically by forming a Schiff base, which changes color from light yellow to pink detectable by the naked eye. A chiral boronic acid based resorcinarene macrocycle (**L3**) was used for the enantiomeric detection of amino acids, specially lysine³⁴. Partial least squares regression modeling of spectral data for macrocycle-lysine guest-host complexes was used to correlate the changes in the turn on fluorescence emission for a various calibration samples of the sensor in the presence of varying enantiomeric compositions of lysine.

Literature survey revealed that most of the papers for the detection of lysine are based on methods like HPLC or chelation by non-fluorescent macrocyclic rings. More research on lysine sensitive fluorescent probes is still awaited.

Histidine :

Yang *et al.* have synthesized a bisporphyrin-based fluorescence sensor (**H1**) which determined histidine by extracting the amino acid into the bulk organic membrane, complexing with the inner metalloporphyrin moiety³⁵. The electron transfer process was thus inhibited, leading to increased fluorescence of the membrane. The optode membrane could determine histidine in aqueous solutions within a limit of 4.5×10^{-6} to 15.3×10^{-6} M.

Another novel turn on sensor may be better called a "chemosensing ensemble" (**H2**), where the fluorescent indicator was bound through non-covalent interactions to the receptor, which quenched its emission³⁶. The added analyte has displaced and released the indicator to the

solution regenerating its full fluorescence. A organic carboxylate bridged dinuclear Cu^{II} complex has been used as receptor for the recognition of histidine, whereas coumarin, fluorescein and eosin were used as indicators.

Fluorescent probes selective for neutral amino acids

Cysteine/Cystine :

Cysteine is one of the essential amino acids of our body. Deficiency of cysteine is responsible for retarded growth, hair depigmentation, edema, lethargy, liver damage, muscle and fat loss, skin lesions, and weakness³⁷. However, it has also been found that elevated levels of various biological cysteines (homocysteine, cysteine, glutathione) are responsible for Alzheimer's disease, Parkinson's disease and various cardiovascular problems³⁸⁻⁴⁰. It is also a potential neurotoxin and a biomarker for many physiological processes. Considering its crucial role in various physiological processes, the design of cysteine sensitive sensors is very important.

Duan *et al.* have designed a symmetrical naphthalimide aldehyde (**C1**) which detected cysteine by fluorescence enhancement with red shift in aqueous solution⁴¹. The fluorescence color has changed from blue to cyan. Upon addition of other amino acids, slight fluorescence quenching was observed without any color change, which indicated that the aldehyde group selectively binds cysteine only. The sensor has been applied for bio-imaging of living cells.

Development of metal clusters as fluorescent probes has been an efficient way of fusing chemistry and nanotechnology. Shang *et al.* have noticed that conjugated polymer-stabilized gold nanoparticles (**C2**) fluoresce weakly due to the fluorescence resonance energy transfer (FRET) between the fluorophore and the gold nanoparticles⁴². Significant enhancement in fluorescence intensity has been observed due to the addition of cysteine while other amino acids did not interfere. Another novel water soluble fluorescent sensor using silver clusters (**C3**) has been developed by the same group of authors for the selective detection of cysteine⁴³. The process consisted of simple mixing of silver salt and poly methacrylic acid (PMAA, a common polyelectrolyte) and subsequent photoreduction. The developed chemosensor was highly sensitive to cysteine.

A chemosensor (**C4**) for Ag⁺ and Fe³⁺ has efficiently

detected cysteine, where the later has been sensed by the *in situ* prepared Ag^+ and Fe^{3+} complexes⁴⁴. The molecular switching between the three chemical inputs (Ag^+ , Fe^{3+} and cysteine) resulted in various molecular logic gates which were integrated to get a sequential information processing device. Addition of increasing amounts of cysteine to the *in situ* Fe^{3+} complex resulted in 'turn on fluorescence' while similar addition to the Ag^+ complex leads to 'turn off fluorescence'. Till date no fluorescent sensors for selective determination of cysteine has been reported.

Glycine :

Highly enantioselective fluorescence response of the binaphthyl macrocycles (**G1**) has been used for the recognition of phenyl glycine⁴⁵. L-Enantiomer of the N-protected phenyl glycine has been found to increase the fluorescence intensity of the binaphthyl fluorophores over 4-fold but the D-enantiomer failed to do so. The work paves the way for further use of binaphthyl macrocycles for the enantioselective detection of amino acid substrates.

Neutral chiral optical sensors (**G2**) containing thio-urea and amide groups were synthesized and efficiently utilized for the enantioselective recognition for α -phenylglycine and phenylglycinol in DMSO⁴⁶.

Alanine and phenyl alanine :

Calixarenes have unique cavity-shaped architecture and pre-organized binding sites which bind to a wide variety of molecules forming host-guest or supramolecular complexes⁴⁷. They act as efficient binding hosts in the fluorescence recognition event, showing enantioselectivity towards certain amino acids. Chiral calix[4]arenes containing hydrazide and dansyl groups (**A1 1**) has been synthesized, which showed enantioselective recognition abilities towards N-protected alanine or phenylalanine anions by turn off fluorescence⁴⁸. The cooperative act of the hydrazide and amide over the bounded amino acid anion with multiple hydrogen bonds has increased the ability of the chiral recognition of these fluorescence chemosensors.

L-Tryptophan, a naturally occurring amino acid possessing both a fluorescent group and a binding unit, has been used earlier in chiral recognition, and has shown good fluorescence response. Qing *et al.* have synthesized two chiral calixarene receptors with L-tryptophan residues (**A1 2**), one of which showed good enantioselective

fluorescent recognition ability towards the N-Boc-protected alanine anion⁴⁹. The fluorescence emission of the chemosensor gradually increased upon addition of *d*- or *l*-alanine anion due to the formation of a 1 : 1 complex between them in DMSO.

The binaphthyl unit with its stable chiral configuration and tunable dihedral angle between the two naphthalene rings, has shown good enantioselectivity in several asymmetric reactions. Xu *et al.*⁵⁰ have efficiently used 1,10-bis-2-naphthol derivatives (**A1 3**) for the chiral recognition of the enantiomers of the N-Boc-protected alanine or phenylalanine anion. A considerable decrease in fluorescence intensity has been observed on binding of the excimer with the (R-) or (S-) alanine or phenylalanine anions, due to the photon induced electron transfer (PET) process. They have also synthesized three chiral receptors (**A1 4**) for the detection of the enantiomers of the N-Boc-protected phenylalanine anion⁵¹.

Kim *et al.*⁵² reported highest chiral selectivity for *t*-Boc alanine using two fluorescent sensors (**A1 5**) which differ by methylene spacers, both bearing same glucopyranosyl units. Furthermore, two sensors have shown opposite D/L selectivity. They have also provided high level theoretical investigations along with 2D-NMR data to support their claim. Most plausibly, host-guest hydrogen bonding interaction and/H- π interaction between anthracene moiety and methyl groups are responsible for such behavior.

Valine and proline :

Cyclodextrins modified with metal binding moieties have been found to be suitable for the coordination of chiral guest molecules around the metal ion⁵³. Corradinni *et al.* have developed fluorescent sensors (**PV 1**) based on modified β -cyclodextrins containing a binding site for Cu^{II} and a dansyl fluorophore^{54,55}. These have been used as enantioselective fluorescence sensors for the discrimination of enantiomers of valine and proline via ligand exchange mechanism. They have suggested that in presence of both Cu^{II} and amino acids, cyclodextrins exhibited enantioselective fluorescence quenching, as per following equilibria :

The enantioselectivity of the process depends on the stereochemistry and conformational properties of the cyclodextrin derivative, giving rise to suitable cyclodextrin-fluorophore interaction which strongly enhances the enantioselectivity of the process. The protocol is very simple and cost effective, and may be applied in industrial, chemical or biotechnological research.

Quantitative measurements of the enantiomeric purities of proline in samples of intermediate composition could be performed by fast fluorescence measurements (accuracy within 5%)⁵⁶ using modified cyclodextrin (**PV 2**).

Introduction of benzylaminomethyl groups at 3,3' position of 1,1' bi-2-naphthol (BINOL)⁵⁷ has produced a highly enantioselective fluorescent sensor (R, S-isomer) (**PV 3**) for N-Boc-proline which caused 57-fold enhancement in the fluorescence intensity of the probe.

Tryptophan :

Tryptophan is generally found at or near the recognition domains of RNA-binding proteins⁵⁸. The recognition phenomenon is responsible for transcriptional regulation, mRNA maturation, RNA interference, translation, and the development of biophysical tools to evaluate these fundamental processes.

Tryptophan has been detected by strong fluorescence enhancement in presence of a tetra amino tripodal zinc(II) complex, with two anthracene units (**Tryp 1**)⁵⁹. A 1 : 1 adduct has been formed with tryptophan, due to a metal-ligand interaction between the Zn^{II} ion and the carboxylate group of the amino acid. Xie *et al.* have reported for the first time a fluorescent ribonucleoside analogue (**Tryp 2**) as a Forster resonance energy transfer acceptor for tryptophan⁶⁰ with visible emission at 440 nm. The FRET pair was found to facilitate the study of RNA binding to native proteins and peptides. Acridine and acridinium compounds with thiourea-binding sites (**Tryp 3**) has been used as an enantioselective fluorescent chemosensor towards L-tryptophan. The polyglycol moiety of the protonated ligand has provided a hydrophobic cavity for selective binding of tryptophan.

Multi-amino acids sensitive sensors

Certain chemosensors could determine more than one amino acid simultaneously by prominent changes of their fluorescence properties.

The development of turn on fluorescence sensors for biologically important amino acids still remains a challenging task, because in most cases fluorescence quenching rather than enhancement has been observed. Sasaki *et al.* have synthesized a receptor based on triaza-18-crown-6 ether combined with two guanidinium groups (**MAA 1**) which could bind several biologically important amino acids like glycine, lysine and γ -aminobutyric acid (GABA) in aqueous methanol solution⁶². Amino acids were detected by a fluorescence enhancement through PET mechanism. The receptor may be used as an indicator for amino acids in aqueous solution or as a component of an optode membrane. Another turn on fluorescence sensor (**MAA 2**) that showed a fluorescence enhancement factor of about 110 was designed by Ryu *et al.*⁶³, which sensed the anionic forms of α -amino acids (e.g. glycinate). Another work in the detection of α -amino acids have utilized the quenching of a conjugated fluorescent polyfluorene by Cu^{II} (**MAA 3**) and the subsequent recovery of fluorescence by the added α -amino acids⁶⁴. A fluorescent cyclophane based on naphthalene and valine (**MAA 4**), could sense L-amino acids like L-alanine, L-valine, L-leucine and L-phenylalanine by a ratiometric phenomenon⁶⁵. The carboxylic groups of these amino acids interacted with the amino groups of the sensor resulting a decrease of the fluorescence intensity at 390 nm and the concomitant increase of the fluorescence at 330 nm.

Mitra *et al.* have designed a chemosensor (**MAA 5**) which displayed a large fluorescence enhancement only in case of aromatic amino acids, like phenyl alanine, tryptophan, histidine and tyrosine⁶⁶. The probe forms 1 : 1 hydrogen bonded complex with the respective amino acid and may be suitably applied for bio-molecular recognition in the near future.

A fluorescent probe (**MAA 6**) for ω -amino acids was developed by Moreno *et al.*, which behaved as a molecular ruler, changing the yellow fluorescent emission into blue as a function of the distance between the terminal ammonium and the carboxylate⁴ groups, permitting the quantitative detection of ω -amino acids⁶⁷. Common basic α -amino acids such as proline, histidine or tryptophan did not change the fluorescence properties, however aqueous solutions of β -alanine, γ -aminobutyric acid (GABA), 5-aminovaleric acid, 6-aminoheptanoic acid or 7-aminoheptanoic acid have caused a dramatic change of

fluorescence from yellow to blue. Cu^{II} complex of quinacridone ligand (MAA 7) has been used to sense amino acids released from various proteases (trypsin, chymotrypsin, subtilisin) where the metal center served as the analyte binding site and the metal coordinating fluorophore as the reporter molecule⁶⁸. This is a rare example of amino acid detection where the process is dependent on the coordinating ability of amino acids for copper without any direct contact between the amino acids and the quinacridone fluorescent reporter. Chimeric fluorescent proteins have been synthesized to detect arginine and ornithine, through fluorescence resonance energy transfer [FRET] mechanism⁶⁹. The sensors could be utilized to monitor *in vivo* dynamics of metabolism and compartmentalization in plants. Cyclodextrins based ditopic receptors (MAA 8) with a metal binding site have been utilized for the enantioselective fluorescence determination of various D- or L-amino acids⁷⁰.

A more recent work has been done on the development of a fluorescent probe (MAA 9) for the determination of histidine and cysteine⁷¹. The Cu²⁺ complex for the detection of histidine tagged protein was developed, based on a dansyl-Gly-Py structure by closely mimicking the structure of a peptide, ATCUN. In aqueous solution, the probe could further detect histidine-rich protein by releasing the quenched fluorescence and hence might be applied for detecting proteins with and without histidine tags either in buffer or foetal bovine serum solutions.

As evident from the above mentioned articles, the fluorescence response of the analyte is guided by competitive complexation reactions between the various amino acids. These sensors can identify and quantify amino acids in various complex biological matrices. However, in most of the papers the analytical figures of merit have not been discussed.

Conclusion :

A thorough survey on the published literature reveals that among the fluorescent sensors developed for determination of trace level amino acids, multi-amino acid sensitive sensors are of highest population. Different metal/metal complexes which have been used for selective determination of amino acids are identified and presented in Table 10. Considerable amount of work has been done on acidic and basic amino acids. However literature on

certain neutral amino acids, i.e. tyrosine, proline, leucine and asparagine are scanty. No fluorescent sensors for the detection of serine, threonine, cystine and methionine have been developed so far. Also, the number of fluorescent probes that work in purely aqueous solution is not sufficient. A limited number of the published literature has reported the different analytical figures of merit. Analytical applications, especially the detection and estimation of different amino acids in various biological samples have been discussed rarely. It may be definitely inferred that this is a very active area of present day research and there is a tremendous scope of the design and application of different fluorescent probes which may work in pure aqueous solutions at physiological pH. Development of such sensors will help to solve many real life challenges regarding trace level determination of amino acids in different biological samples in a simple, rapid and greener way.

Acknowledgement

Contribution of the members of our research group who have helped in literature survey or with their own research work is gratefully acknowledged.

References

1. L. Prodi, *New J. Chem.*, 2005, **29**, 20.
2. M. H. Lim and S. J. Lippard, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 2007, **40**, 41.
3. B. Valeur and I. Leray, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 2003, **205**, 3.
4. M. Shamsipur, K. Alizadeh, M. Hosseini, C. Caltagirone and V. Lippolis, *Sens. Actuators (B)*, 2006, **113**, 892.
5. M. C. Aragoni, M. Area, A. Bencini, A. J. Blake, C. Caltagirone, G. D. Filippo, F. A. Devillanova, A. Garau, T. Gelbrich, M. B. Hurssthouse, F. Isaia, V. Lippolis, M. Mameli, P. Mariani, B. Valtancoli and C. Wilson, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2007, **46**, 4548.
6. I. Stibor and P. Zlatuskova, *Top. Curr. Chem.*, 2005, **255**, 31.
7. F. Ma, L. Shen, X. Ai and C. Zhang, *Org. Lett.*, 2007, **9**, 125.
8. G. Y. Qing, Y. B. He, Y. Zhao, C. G. Hu, S. Y. Liu and X. Yang, *Eur. J. Org. Chem.*, 2006, 1574.
9. M. Ali, M. Jha, S. K. Das and S. K. Saha, *J. Phys. Chem. (B)*, 2009, **113**, 15563.
10. R. M. Mánéz and F. Sancenón, *Chem. Rev.*, 2003, **103**, 4419.
11. L. Pu, *Chem. Rev.*, 2004, **104**, 1687.
12. X. F. Mei and C. Wolf, *Chem. Commun.*, 2004, 2078.

13. S. L. Tobey, B. D. Jones and E. V. Anslyn, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2003, **125**, 4026.
14. A. P. de Silva, H. Q. N. Gunaratne, T. M. Gunnlaugsson, A. J. Huxley, C. P. McCoy, J. T. Rademacher and T. E. Rice, 1997, **97**, 1515.
15. B. S. Meldrum, *J. Nutr.*, 2000, **130**, 1007.
16. G. D. Pearlson, *Ann. Neurol.*, 2000, **48**, 556.
17. K. M. Davis and J. Y. Wu, *J. Biomed. Sci.*, 2001, **8**, 7.
18. D. M. Treiman, *Epilepsia Suppl.*, 2001, **42**, 8.
19. M. B. Jorgensen and N. H. Diemer, *Acta Neurol. Scand.*, 1982, **66**, 535.
20. T. Wieloch, *Science*, 1985, **230**, 681.
21. E. G. McGeer, J. W. Olney and P. L. McGeer (eds.), "Kainic Acid as a Tool in Neurobiology", Raven Press, New York, 1987, 95.
22. R. N. Weinreb and L. A. Levin, *Arch. Ophthalmol.*, 1999, **117**, 1540.
23. E. B. Dreyer, D. Zurakowski and R. A. Schumer, *Arch. Ophthalmol.*, 1996, **114**, 299.
24. N. J. Sucher, S. A. Lipton and E. B. Dreyer, *Vision Res.*, 1997, **37**, 3483.
25. S. Y. Liu, L. Fang, Y. B. He, W. H. Chan, K. T. Yeung, Y. K. Cheng and R. H. Yang, *Org. Lett.*, 2005, **7/26**, 5825.
26. H. Guan, P. Zhou, X. Zhou and Z. He, *Talanta*, 2008, **77**, 319.
27. G. Y. Qing, T. Sun, Z. Chen, X. Yang, X. Wu and Y. He, *Chirality*, 2009, **21**, 363.
28. G. Y. Qing, Z. H. Chen, F. Wang, X. Yang, L. Z. Meng and Y. B. He, *Chinese J. Chem.*, 2008, **26**, 721.
29. S. Das, S. Guha, A. Banerjee and D. Das, *Org. Biomol. Chem.*, 2011, **9/20**, 7097.
30. H. Yoshida, Y. Nakano, K. Koiso, H. Nohta, J. Ishida and M. Yamaguchi, *Anal. Sci.*, 2001, **17**, 107.
31. C. Hirayama, K. Suyama, Y. Horie, K. Tanimoto and S. Kato, *Biochem. Med. Metab. Biol.*, 1987, **38**, 127.
32. C. P. Mandl and B. König, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2005, **70**, 670.
33. Y. Zhou, J. Won, J. Y. Lee and J. Yoon, *Chem. Commun.*, 2011, **47**, 1997.
34. G. I. Richard, H. M. Marwani, S. Jiang, S. O. Fakayode, M. Lowry, R. M. and I. M. Warner, *Appl. Spectrosc.*, 2008, **62**, 476.
35. R. Yang, K. Wang, L. Long, D. Xiao, X. Yang and W. Tan, *Anal. Chem.*, 2002, **74**, 1088.
36. M. A. Hortala, L. Fabbrizzi, N. Marcotte, F. Stomeo and A. Taglietti, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2003, **125**, 20.
37. S. Shahrokhian, *Anal. Chem.*, 2001, **73**, 5972.
38. A. M. Troen, *Prog. Neuropsychopharmacol Biol. Psychiatry*, 2005, **29**, 1140.
39. C. Babiloni, P. Bosco, R. Ghidoni, C. D. Percio, R. Squitti, G. Binetti, I. Benussi, R. Ferri, G. Frisoni, B. Lanuzza, E. Cassetta, G. Anello, M. Gurzi, S. Bartesaghi, R. Lizio, M. Tombini and P. M. Rossini, *Neuroscience*, 2007, **145**, 942.
40. J. O. Elliott, M. P. Jacobson and Z. Haneef, *Epilepsy Res.*, 2007, **76**, 113.
41. L. Duan, Y. Xu, X. Qian, F. Wang, J. Liu and T. Cheng, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2008, **49**, 6624.
42. L. Shang, C. J. Qin, T. Wang, M. Wang, L. X. Wang and S. J. Dong, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 2007, **111**, 13414.
43. L. Shang and S. Dong, *Biosens. Bioelectron.*, 2009, **24**, 1569.
44. M. Kumar, R. Kumar and V. Bhalla, *Org. Lett.*, 2011, **13/3**, 366.
45. J. Lin, Z-B. Li, H-C. Zhang and L. Pu, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2004, **45**, 103.
46. X. H. Huang, Y. B. He, C. G. Hu and Z. H. Chen, *J. Fluorescence*, 2009, **19/1**, 97.
47. Z. Asfari, V. Böhmer, J. Harrowfield and J. Vicens (eds.), "Calixarenes", Kluwer Academic Publishers, Dordrecht, 2001.
48. S. Y. Liu, Y. B. He, G. Y. Qing, K. X. Xu and H. J. Qin, *Tetrahedron Asymm.*, 2005, **16**, 1527.
49. G. Y. Qing, Y. B. He, F. Wang, H. J. Qin, C. G. Hu and X. Yang, *Eur. J. Org. Chem.*, 2007, 1768.
50. K. X. Xu, Z. Qiu, J. J. Zhao, J. Zhao and C. J. Wang, *Tetrahedron Asymm.*, 2009, **20**, 1690.
51. K. X. Xu, G. Y. Qing, Y. B. He, H. J. Qin and L. Hu, *Supramol. Chem.*, 2007, **19**, 403.
52. Y. K. Kim, H. N. Lee, N. J. Singh, H. J. Choi, J. Y. Xue, K. S. Kim, J. Yoon and M. H. Hyun, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2008, **73**, 301.
53. G. Impellizzeri, G. Maccarrone, E. Rizzarelli, G. Vecchio, R. Corradini and R. Marchelli, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.*, 1991, **30**, 1348.
54. R. Corradini, C. Pagnuzzi, R. Marchelli, S. Pagliari, S. Sforza, A. Dossena, G. Galaverna and A. Duchateau, *Chirality*, 2003, **15**, S30.
55. R. Corradini, C. Paganuzzi, R. Marchelli, S. Pagliari, S. Sforza, A. Dossena, G. Galaverna and A. Duchateau, *J. Mater. Chem.*, 2005, **15**, 2741.
56. S. Pagliari, R. Corradini, G. Galaverna, S. Sforza, A. Dossena, M. Montaiti, L. Prodi, N. Zaccheroni and R. Marchelli, *Chem. Eur. J.*, 2004, **10**, 2749.
57. X. He, X. Cui, M. Li, L. Lin, X. Liu and X. Feng, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2009, **50**, 5853.
58. C. M. Baker and H. G. Grant, *Biopolymers*, 2007, **85**, 456.
59. L. Fabbrizzi, M. Licchelli, A. Perotti, A. Poggi, G. Rabaioli, D. Sacchi and A. Taglietti, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans.*, 2001, **2/11**, 2108.

60. Y. Xie, T. Maxson and Y. Tor, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2010, **132**, 11896.
61. A. Sirikulajorn, P. Duanglaor and B. T. Tuntulani, *Supramol. Chem.*, 2009, **21/6**, 486.
62. S. Sasaki, A. Hashizume, D. Citterio, E. Fujii and K. Suzuki, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2002, **43**, 7243.
63. D. Ryu, E. Park, D. S. Kim, S. Yan, J. Y. Lee, B. Y. Chang and K. H. Ahn, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2008, **130**, 2394.
64. Z. A. Li, X. D. Lou, Z. Li and J. G. Qin, *ACS Appl. Mat. Interfaces*, 2009, **1/2**, 232.
65. F. Galindo, J. Becerril, M. Isabel Burguete, S. V. Luis and L. Vigara, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2004, **45**, 1659.
66. A. Mitra, J. P. Chinta and C. P. Rao, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2010, **51**, 139.
67. D. Moreno, J. V. Cuevas, G. García-Herbosa and T. Torroba, *Chem. Commun.*, 2011, **47**, 3183.
68. K. E. S. Dean, G. Klein, O. Renaudet and J. L. Reymond, *Bioorg. Med. Chem. Lett.*, 2003, **13**, 1653.
69. M. Bogner and U. Ludewig, *J. Fluorescence*, 2007, **17**, 350.
70. R. Corradini, C. Paganuzzi, R. Marchelli, S. Pagliari, A. and A. Duchateau, *J. Incl. Phenom. Macro. Chem.*, 2007, **57**, 625.
71. B. Wang, Y. Gao, H. W. Li, Z. P. Hu and Y. Wu, *Org. Biomol. Chem.*, DOI : 10.1039/e1ob05372h.

